

Exploring the Levels of Social Media Addiction among Working and Non-Working Women within Mumbai and its Metropolitan Areas.

DhwaniKataria

Psychology Student, SIES Institute of
Comprehensive Education Mumbai, Maharashtra

Abstract:- Social networking has become the need of the hour, especially amidst the uncertainty of the pandemic. The distinguishing feature of this media is the two-way, immediate communication it provides in contrast to other channels of traditional media like television and print, where interaction is only one-way. Due to these very advantages of the online world, having a presence on social media has become a rudimentary procedure for any organisation. This study was descriptive in nature and aimed at exploring the level of social networking addiction among working and non-working women in the age group of 40 - 45 years in Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, and Thane by the use of the social networking addiction scale given by M.G. Shahnawaz and Usama Rehman. The sample comprised of 298 participants. The findings of the study provided a rather interesting inference which indicated a low level of addiction among working and non-working women. Overall these findings suggest that although the addiction level in this age group is lower, there are also no such significant differences seen between the addiction level of working and non-working women.

Keywords:- Social media addiction, working, non-working, women, Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, Thane.

I. INTRODUCTION

Individuals of all ages may now utilise social media effectively thanks to easy access to the internet and technological tools. Social media is a type of online communication. Users of social networking platforms can engage in conversations, share information, and produce digital content. There are numerous social media platforms, including blogs, microblogs, wikis, social networking sites, photo and video sharing platforms, instant messaging, podcasts, widgets, virtual reality, and more (Smith, 2019). The use of social media applications has become an integral element of daily life. Healthy social media use encourages people to engage numerous abilities, such as reading, writing, selecting, and categorising, while gathering information. Uncontrolled social media use, on the other hand, may have a negative impact on a person's physical, mental, social, and cognitive development (Mayda, A., 2015).

Behavioural addiction, defined as the inability to resist an inclination and an incentive to execute an action that hurts the person or others, encompasses technology addiction kinds such as internet, smartphone, game, and

social media addiction (Senturk, E., 2017). Addiction terminology is commonly used physically in the literature. Pathological use/abuse of any chemical or stimulant, according to DSM-IV, is not characterised as... addiction." Instead, internet addiction is defined as "problematic/pathological usage of the internet" (Davis, R.A., 2001). The following are symptoms of online addiction, and hence social media addiction, which is a sub-category of internet addiction: an increase in the frequency of internet use, lying about the amount and duration of use, constantly engaging one's mind with the internet and its components, using the internet to prevent difficulties, and exhibiting continuing usage while being aware of the effects of excessive internet use (Sally, L.P.M., 2006). Physical and mental illnesses, increased stagnation, sleeplessness, and wrath are some of the other behavioural impacts. As a result, social consequences may include a loss of work and leisure interests, as well as social isolation.

A. Types of Social Media

Today, social media is used by over 97% of marketers to interact with their target audiences. But you could be wondering which kind of platforms you should be on if you're involved with developing a social media strategy for your business or simply using these sites for varied personal purposes. There are more social media platforms available nowadays, and popular ones like Facebook are constantly developing and introducing new features. It might be difficult to decide which social channels to employ because of the growing requirement for a social presence and the overwhelming number of platform options. Through this, I shall now discuss some of the core types of social media and the uses of each of them.

- The most conventional kind of social media is social networking. Platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn are sometimes referred to as "networking" platforms since they allow user accounts to communicate with one another in a variety of ways.
- Social Media types such as media sharing are used to search and share images, video, live sessions and other sorts of media on the internet. Consider Instagram, Snapchat, and YouTube.
- Discussion Forums are used to find, share, and debate various types of information, thoughts, and news. For example, social media sites such as Quora or Reddit.
- Social Media sites such as Pinterest will allow you to discover, share, debate and store a range of popular content.

- When it comes to consumer review sites such as Zomato or TripAdvisor, the user gets to learn and share reviews about that product or brand. You can give them ratings as well. When a company receives good feedback on these platforms, their claims become more trustworthy since the feedback acts as Social Proof.
- Sites like WordPress or Tumblr are used for publishing, posting comments, blogs and other content material.

B. Frequency of Usage

Since its inception in 1996, social media has reached half of the 7.7 billion people worldwide. The number of users across all social networking platforms has almost tripled in the last ten years, rising from 960 million in 2010 to 4.47 billion in July 2021.

Globally, 4.48 billion people use social media. Social media has had 12.5% annual growth on average since 2015. As evidenced by the 9.2 percent growth rate for the 2019–2020 period, growth is, however, declining. The top five countries in growth rate are Asia, Africa, South America, North America, Europe, and Australasia.

Social media is used by people worldwide for an average of 2 hours and 24 minutes every day; if someone joined at the age of 16 and lived to be 70, they would've spent 5.7 years of life on it. The most widely used social media platform is Facebook, which has an active of 2.9 billion users on a monthly basis, ahead of WhatsApp (2 billion) and YouTube (2.3 billion).

C. How much of the population is active on social media?

56.8% of the world's population is currently active on social media. According to network usage rates amongst eligible users, 85% of the 5 billion smartphone owners and 93.33% of the 4.8 billion internet users worldwide utilise social media.

D. How many accounts on social media does the typical person have?

A member of Generation Z has, on average, has 8.4 accounts globally, up from 4.8 accounts in 2014, as per the Global Web Index (2020). In that study of 46 countries with internet users between the ages of 16 and 64, Japan had the least social network accounts (3.8 per person), while India had the most.

E. Social Media and Gender Difference

Currently, 54% of those who use social media worldwide are men and 46% of those are women. Women, however, are the most active users in the United States: 76% of them have accounts on social networks as opposed to 72% of males.

Men & women engage on social networking sites in distinct ways based on where they are. The gender gap may be most apparent in terms of platform utilisation. Apps like Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook have greater male user indices when compared to the main eight social media networks by active users per month. Sites like Pinterest, which has a disproportionately female readership, are more female-oriented than Instagram and Facebook.

F. Usage as per Education & Income

Interestingly, the fastest-growing demographic of Facebook users is those over 65. Currently, 46% of Facebook users are 65 or older. Teenage usage of the network has decreased during the past several years. For instance, 71% of teenagers used Facebook regularly in 2015. That has now decreased to 51%. 74% of high wage-earners (those making over \$75,000) who use Facebook are also active users. The percentage of Facebook users with a college degree is 74%. India has the most users as of 2020, with a maximum of 270 million. Currently, 63% of men and 75% of women use Facebook.

The demographic group with the maximum number of users is now between the age groups of 18 and 24. 43.7% of users on Instagram are male, whereas 56.3% of users are female. Geographically speaking, the U.S. has 116 million users, which is the largest. India comes in second with 79 million users. 42% of these users reside in rural regions, compared to 32% who live in metropolitan areas. Instagram is also used by 42% of those who hold college degree or more and 33% of those with only a high school diploma.

G. Factors affecting the use of social media

In the modern era, social media has become the latest fad. Everyone now uses social media on a regular basis and it has essentially become the language of this generation. Furthermore, it should be highlighted that social networking sites is used by individuals of various ages and is not just popular among millennials.

Social media has not only made our lifestyle and experiences exceptional, but also a medium to promote, advertise, and disseminate awareness. Whether it's posting or sharing one's memories on Instagram or Facebook or even making a comment or putting down one's viewpoint, perhaps on a site like Twitter.

The primary motivation for using social media globally, according to a 2017 GWI survey on social media management trends, was to stay in contact with friends, which accounted for 40% of internet users. Our most recent data, however, from 2021, shows that internet users now are virtually as likely to frequent social media sites to remain in contact with peers as they are to remain up to date on news or events.

This shift in social behaviour towards the use of the internet as a medium of entertainment and news, shows how social interactions are changing. It also helps explain why Facebook is placing a lot of money into Watch (its video hub), and why Bloomberg Media & Twitter are working together on TikTok, a network for live-streamed media coverage. The last few options on the list are really for sharing private data or material (such photos, movies, or ideas). This demonstrates that passive and purposeful activities are becoming appealing to digital users.

The survey that was earlier conducted by the GWI in 2017, indicated a few of the top reasons for use of social media amongst people. This included: (i) staying up to date with current news and events, (ii) getting in touch with friends and family, (iii) to fill up spare time, (iv) to find

entertaining content and (v) to research and find products to buy.

H. Impact of Covid-19 on social media usage

Through a linked network, social media sites like Instagram, Twitter, Facebook and others let people influence the decisions of many. Since they are no longer separate realities, physical reality and the online virtual world are not significantly distinct from one another. Events offline have an impact on online behaviours, and vice versa is true for the majority of the time (Louni & Subbalakshmi, 2014).

As a result of COVID-19, there have been fewer in-person social encounters, but there are now more connections made online than ever before. For instance, social media engagement rose by 60% during the pandemic's initial wave (Fullerton, N., 2021). Social media has for many individuals become their only connection to the external world, especially when people search for methods to stay amused and connected.

The necessity for improved connectivity was obvious from the onset of the epidemic. As users adjusted to a new, shared world, it was clear from different challenges such as the "#ice bucket challenge" and pictures of parties on online platforms such as Zoom, that they wanted to remain active (Zhao, N., 2020). Nevertheless, after a year or so, difficulties related to pandemic subsided, and social media accounts are returning to several of the old hazards that have long made them problematic for mental wellbeing, such as false information and extensively altered photographs.

Users, particularly the ones who are using social networking sites more regularly, are impacted by these implausible portrayals. For instance, those who have been diagnosed with social phobia and anxiety issues are already more likely to suffer the harmful effects of social media.

Excessive screen usage has effects that go well beyond people who experience social anxiety. Many people feel less connected as compared to the pre-epidemic world since there are less possibilities for in-person engagement as a result of the pandemic, despite their best efforts to use social networking platforms to improve connectedness. Rather, psychologist Melissa G. Hunt, (assistant director of clinical training in Penn's Psychology department), discovered that social media use worsens sadness and loneliness in the initial experimental research on the use of apps such as Instagram, Facebook and Snapchat.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Political action, voting education, as well as the quick dissemination of information have all found major and potent platforms on social media. In contemporary times, anyone without a profile on social media is viewed as being 'behind the times'. Personally and professionally our life now, on both aspects, revolves around social media platforms. An average mobile phone user can't spend a day without visiting a social media site. Social networking sites may therefore be effectively utilised to target certain voters,

encourage people to take advantage of their voting rights and disseminate information. Social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram are just a handful that encourage users to have greater political engagement. An expanding corpus of research suggests that excessive SNS usage is connected to symptoms that are typically attributed to drug addiction.

Extensive use of technology by teens has, based on 2014 research, negatively impacted their academic performance, weight, activity levels, and most importantly, their physical and psychological health. Twenty-one percent of adults and forty percent of teenagers confess to accessing social networking sites while using the toilet. The question that arises is what makes it so difficult for us to get away from social media, even for a short while? Social media is addicting, research claims. Studies show that all the likes on Facebook and retweets on Twitter have changed the reward center of our brains. Engaging on social media platforms has now become like injecting dopamine right into the body. Social media use activates the brain's reward system, which is regarded to be the primary cause of addictive behavior.

In order to understand the origin of social media addiction, Griffiths MD (2013) has given three primary theoretical theories that might not be mutually incompatible (Turel and Serenko).

The cognitive-behavioral model proposes that "abnormal" social media usage develops from cognitive biases, is aggravated by a variety of contextual factors, and ultimately develops into obsessive and/or addictive social networking. Although the social skill model emphasizes how people's lack of self-presentational skills and inclination towards online interaction over in-person interactions lead to "abnormal" social networking, which ultimately results in compulsive and/or addictive use of social media, The socio-cognitive paradigm is the last model that he discusses. It highlights the fact that "abnormal" networking via social media develops as a result of the expectation of favorable outcomes, which, when coupled with weak internet self-efficacy and inadequate internet self-regulation, results in compulsive and/or addictive social networking. These three theories propose that the shift from typical to harmful social networking use takes place when an individual starts to view social networking to be an important coping mechanism for anxiety, loneliness, stress, or depression.

P.T. Ayeni (2019) discusses 5 indicators that highlight one's predisposition to social networking addiction, which lends credence to the aforementioned arguments. The very first one is titled "Cooking for Instagram sharing." What is more essential when you prepare a lovely salad for dinner? Taking a picture to share via social media or devouring the salad? The aesthetic appeal of food has surpassed the applicability due to Instagram's growing influence. The next indication focuses on disclosing all of your activities at any moment. The writer of "The Distraction Addiction," Alex Soojung-Kim Pang (2020), claims that rather than what one accomplishes in the real world, one is more concerned

with the amount of fun they have or what they engage in on social media.

According to Ayeni (2019), the most crucial sign is when we know all about a person we know hardly anything about in the real world because of social media. Information about our surroundings, activities, friends, family members and breakfast consumption is generally accessible to us. This even opens up the door to a level of closeness that is sometimes unattainable with true friends.

Jealousy is just one of the symptoms that your consumption of social networking sites has become dangerously out of control. We can now follow individuals as they travel to far-off areas, attend festivals, and participate in activities thanks to our continual media access. It is now much easier to create digital personas since we can choose what information to reveal. The fact that you can only see a limited portion of reality online is something that you are subconsciously aware of but frequently choose to overlook. Hence, your social media addiction has reached a critical peak if jealousy over your friends' festivities, presents, houses, automobiles, spouses, and even physical features has started to surface. According to a 2019 survey by Addiction Resources, the average American views their smartphone every 13 minutes, with one in 10 doing so every 4 minutes. They become anxious when they are not able to do so. This just serves to highlight how reliant we are on the internet and how addiction to social media is becoming a serious problem.

Another factor that could contribute to the negative impact of social networking addiction is self-esteem. Users of social media are continually exposed to other people's carefully chosen and romanticized online selves, which may impair the viewers' self-esteem, as per the Hyper Personal Model (Gonzales & Hancock, 2010). Even though they don't know the individual users offline, frequent users of Facebook, for instance, think that other people are more content and accomplished than they are (Chou & Edge, 2012). It's likely that addiction to social media makes people feel less confident about themselves, which in turn affects their academic performance and mental well-being (Rosenberg & Egbert, 2011). In other words, the relationship between social media addiction to mental health and academic achievement may be mediated by self-esteem.

Two studies were undertaken by Hou, Y., Xiong, D., Jiang, T., Song, L., & Wang, Q. (2019) in order to better understand how addiction to social media affects people's psychological well-being and academic achievement. In the first study, they investigated the relationships between university students' academic achievement, mental health and social media addiction, as well as the role of self-esteem as a potential mediating factor. A questionnaire was given to the participants which covered all 4 parameters mentioned above. Based on the results of the first study, they devised an empirical intervention in the second study to decrease reliance on social media and enhance the psychological health and academic achievement of college students. In all investigations, social media addiction was measured using the Bergen Social Media Addiction Scale (BSMAS;

Andreassen et al., 2017). Based on the general theory of addiction, Andreassen and colleagues (2012) developed the Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS), which has 6 items that each define a hallmark of compulsive behavior (i.e., salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal symptoms, conflict, and relapse). The scale has strong psychometric properties, and there are two scoring options for the addiction: polythetic (3 or higher on at least four of the six questions) or monothetic (3 or higher on all six items) (Andreassen et al., 2012). The fact that BFAS focuses on Facebook usage and may not be suitable for many people is one critique of the program (Griffiths, 2012). Eventually, based on the results of earlier studies, they proposed that social media addiction would have a detrimental impact on college student's psychological well-being and academic achievement and that these interactions would be regulated by the self-esteem of students (e.g., Jiang et al., 2016; Koc&Gulyagci, 2013; Pantic et al., 2012; Valkenburg et al., 2006).

The research was carried out by Zhao, L. (2021) to look at yet another aspect of internet addiction. His research sought to examine the effects of various social media usage patterns on addiction to social media and emotional well-being along with the link between the two. He gathered a pool of 370 university students from China using random sampling. The respondents were split into addicted and non-addicted groups based on their ratings on a social networking addiction scale. As a part of his research technique, he used a social usage scale that included three questions from a study by Chang and Zhu (2011): "I can make some new friends on the internet," "I can discover old friends through social media," and "I can remain in contact with my friends through social media." The second one consisted of the Entertainment Use Scale, which comprised three items overall and was based on research by Guo et al. (2013) and Pang (2018b). The phrases "I can use social media is to enjoy pleasure and enjoyment," "I can use social networking sites is to look at what occurred with the people around me," and "I can use social networking sites is to spend time online" were among them.

The third one, The Bergen Social Media Addiction Scale, which comprised eighteen questions like "Spent a significant amount of time pondering over social or planned usage of social media?" and "Felt a desire to use social media ever more?" was utilized in the study (Andreassen et al., 2012). Based on his study, he came to the conclusion that addicted students score better on entertainment and social usage than non-addicted students, which is consistent with earlier research (Hormes et al., 2014), i.e., addicted users spend more time online. Contrarily, students who are not addicted perform better on a subjective well-being scale than those who are, suggesting that non-addicted students may frequently experience higher subjective well-being (Bachnio et al., 2016). In order to prevent social media addiction and enhance subjective wellbeing, families and colleges should monitor students' usage of social media and provide them with advice on how to use it responsibly.

The usage of social media, as well as the internet, has increased dramatically recently, having an impact on everyone's lives. After discussing this in the studies on university students previously mentioned, it is crucial to pay attention to its consequences on young adults, a cohort for whom the distinction between online and offline interaction is essentially nonexistent and for whom the presence of compulsive Internet use may have a negative impact on their lives.

Aresearch published in 2014, Shahnaz, I., and Rezaul Karim, A.K.M. investigated the effects of young people's addiction to social media on subjective wellbeing and life involvement. The study involved 210 college students in total. One of the many facets of good mental well-being is life satisfaction. It alludes to the cognitive and adjudicative process. The purpose of life is referred to in the current study's focus on life involvement. It also describes engaging in behaviors that support life.

Pertaining to the measurements and methods utilized in this research, participants completed a questionnaire that included questions about how much time they spend online, how frequently they access social media, how long they spend online each day, the types of online activities they engage in, and the websites they visit. It was anticipated after reviewing the pertinent research that social media addiction would have a detrimental effect on personal satisfaction and life engagement. At the University of Dhaka, information was gathered from 210 graduates in order to evaluate these predictions. The Internet Addiction Test, Satisfaction with Life Scale, and Life Engagement Test measures were given to them in accordance with the established methods (Shahnaz, I., 2014). The findings back up the hypotheses of the study.

According to the ratings on Internet addiction as well as its dimensions, there are differences in the level of Internet addiction depending on why a person uses the Internet. In the current study, online debate, adult chatting, online gaming, talking, cyber engagement, and viewing porn were the Internet uses that were most related with ratings on Internet addiction and its dimensions, whereas searching, downloading, and emailing were the least common uses. There are, however, certain restrictions on this study. First, a reasonable number of volunteers were used in the study (i.e., 210). Second, only students of the University of Dhaka were conveniently chosen for the sample. Therefore, the results cannot be applied to other Internet groups.

The results of the current study improve our knowledge of the structure of social media addiction and its effects on overall happiness and life involvement despite the aforementioned constraints. Bangladeshi citizens will become more socially conscious as a result of the evidence showing how Internet addiction negatively affects life satisfaction and involvement. According to the transmission of various media (e.g., magazines, television, Internet blogging), young people in the nation are susceptible to a range of social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. These broadcasts' findings are consistent with those of the current investigation. These results can thus be

utilized to provide useful recommendations for the patients to aid in their correct Internet usage. The research could also be utilized to develop social media management techniques and to support administrators and policymakers in the detection, prevention, and rehabilitation of social media addiction.

When the covid-19 pandemic struck the entire world, people were forced to recon with their with their own feelings as they came to terms with their subjective reality. There was not much accurate information available throughout the Covid-19 pandemic phases. Content on social media shared by creators produced a plethora of falsehoods and incomplete ideas. As in previous pandemics, lack of reliable information coupled with a rising death rate led to panic, confusion, and the cessation of critical reasoning and fact-checking skills. As a result of the panic, the WHO ultimately released a "massive infodemic" of COVID-19 lies. On the other hand, it also produced straightforward infographics and material, published factual information, and used social media accounts. Social networking websites including Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, and TikTok simultaneously took action to clean up their own networks (Parikh, Desai, & Parikh, 2020).

The objective of the research conducted by David, S., and Warriar, U. (2021) is to comprehend the prevalence and critical importance of social media addiction and abuse during the COVID-19 lockdown. Since the majority of people either work from home or attend school there, it is obvious that neither of them is very adept at managing their time or multitasking. Due to their extended work weeks and the subsequent emergence of disorganized and chaotic routines, the majority of individuals are vulnerable to burnout and stress. Regardless of background or age, the current COVID Crisis has significantly contributed to the derangement of peoples' lifestyles. Nevertheless, a significant portion of the population has found it simpler to adapt to the changing normal as well as the new lifestyle, while the other half of people are still finding it challenging to shift in the middle of the difficult times. The influence of social media and its effects on people during the current COVID-19 issue has been the subject of several research papers. The majority of them are the result of research on the tainting effects of social isolation and its impacts.

The 203 young individuals (aged 18 to 30) who participated in the study—some of whom were single, wedded, or engaged—were surveyed online via the Google questionnaire to gather the data. A sample of the t-test was used to compute the inter-item validity, reliability, and consistency coefficient (Davids, S., 2021). The majority of respondents were found to be keen to utilize social media and explore online platforms in order to stay updated on the material posted by their respective groups on social media, according to the study's findings. Additionally, individuals frequently spend more time online, particularly on social networking sites, while they are alone as opposed to whenever they are among other people.

Addiction to social media is predicted to progressively rise as the internet becomes a necessary component of daily life. Excessive usage of social media platforms can have negative effects on a person's mental, physical, and social health in addition to impairing their ability to perform in social situations. Teenagers are the demographic most susceptible to developing a social media addiction. In relation to the operational shift of the "digital age," it is vital to take into account new health policies surrounding this. By examining the above-mentioned studies, I have tried to highlight the various aspects of social media addiction, both, in the past as well as the current times. Through my study, I will attempt to further examine various dimensions to the use of social media by conducting primary and secondary research. I hope it will contribute to the current database of social media addiction that has important theoretical and practical implications.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the different types of social networking platforms used by working and non-working women residing in Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, and Thane.
- To understand the frequency and duration of usage of social networking within the age group of 40-45 years.
- To study the level of social networking addiction among working and non-working women residing in Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, and Thane.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Participants

Participants in this study comprised of 298 samples out of which 173 were working and 125 were non-working women of age group 40-45 years residing within Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, and Thane. Given the ongoing pandemic crisis and the numerous limitations with regard to the place and time at the point of data collection, convenience sampling was used. Convenience sampling is a type of non-probability sampling technique where subjects are selected because of their convenient approachability to the researcher (Science Direct, 2010).

B. Materials

The survey method was used by the means of Google forms to collect the responses from the participants and analyse the data further. The survey form consisted of two parts:

- Part 1: Was devised by the researcher to elicit data that would contribute to information pertaining to background information of the participants, the type of social networking platforms used, the frequency and duration of usage. This part was constructed by creating a conceptual framework and then creating items and categories for the same.
- Part 2: A scale designed during the year 2020 by M.G. Shahnawaz and Usama Rehman to measure social media addiction was used. According to Griffith's (2005) component framework, which stresses the salience, mood modulation, resistance, conflict, relapse, and, withdrawal dimensions of addictions, the measure is made up of 21 questions divided into distinct categories (Griffith, 2005). On a scale of one to ten, the respondents were asked to choose the figure that best represented their choice. By adding up each participant's choice of items, the rating was completed. The range of the scoring system was 21–127. A rating of 84 or higher indicates addiction (Rehman, 2020). In a period of 25 days, the test-retest reliability of the scale was 88 percent (Rehman, 2020). The scale's validity for convergence and divergence was also confirmed.

C. Design and Procedure

The research design was descriptive in nature as it aimed at exploring the current use of social media networking, the different types of networking platforms used and the frequency and duration of usage. Consent was sought from the participants and those who consented were directly led to the survey pertaining to this study. The sample selected were from personal, random contacts as well as acquaintances. The first round of google form link was shared within my personal contacts. Next, with the help of my friends and colleagues, I was able to connect to their parents, relatives and friends who met the study's age criteria and were able to circulate it to others, requesting them to share it ahead. Lastly, I shared the link on social media networking platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, LinkedIn and Instagram to target specific accounts and groups to collect the desired number of responses. The time taken to complete the forms by each participant was approximately 5 to 7 minutes.

D. Plan of Data Analysis & Demographics

The data was analysed quantitatively using frequency and percentage. The number mentioned in the brackets () below, refers to the distribution of percentage in that data. The score obtained from the social networking addiction scales was used to ascertain whether there was a problem of addiction within the sample.

Employment Status	Number of women (in frequency and %)
Employed	173 (58.05)
Unemployed	125 (41.94)

Table 1: Employment Status

According to Table 1, out of our total 298 samples, 173 (58.05) were working women and 125 (41.94) were non-working women.

No. of Children	Number of women
0	50 (16.77)
1	100 (33.35)
2	138 (46.30)
3	9 (3.02)
4	1 (0.33)

Table 2: No. of children

According to the data displayed in Table no 2, a majority of 138 (46.30) samples had 2 children, followed by 100 (33.55) samples having 1 child, 50 (16.77) samples having no children, 9 (3.02) samples having 3 children and only 1 (0.33) woman having 4 children.

Family Dynamics	Number
Nuclear	146 (48.99)
Joint	90 (30.20)
Living alone	19 (6.37)
Living with parents	39 (13.08)
Extended Family	4 (1.34)

Table 3: Family Dynamics

According to Table 3, 146 (48.99) samples belong from a nuclear family, 90 (30.20) samples living in a joint family, 39 (13.08) of them were living with parents, 19 (6.37) of them living alone and 4 (1.34) women lived with their extended family.

Relationship Status	Number of women
Single	19 (6.37)
Never married	9 (3.02)
Married	241 (80.87)
Unmarried	11 (3.69)
Widow	6 (2.01)
Divorced	12 (4.02)

Table 4: Relationship Status

From the Table 4, out of 298 samples, 241 (80.87) samples were married, 19 (6.37) were single, 12 (4.02) were divorced, 11 (3.69) were unmarried, 9 (3.02) were never married and 6 (2.01) were widows.

Age (in years)	Number of women
40	64 (21.47)
41	31 (10.40)
42	36 (12.08)
43	38 (12.75)
44	41 (13.75)
45	88 (29.53)

Table 5: Age Group Distribution

According to Table 5, out of 298 samples, 64 (21.47) samples are 40 years old, 31 (10.40) samples are 41 years old, 36 (12.08) samples are 42 years old, 38 (12.75) samples are 43 years old, 41 (13.75) samples are 44 years old and 88 (29.53) samples are 45 years old.

District	Number of women
Mumbai	198 (66.44)
Navi Mumbai	41 (47.31)
Thane	59 (58.35)

Table 6: District Distribution

According to Table 6, out of 298 samples, 198 (66.44) samples reside in Mumbai, 59 (53.35) samples reside in Thane and 41 (47.31) are from Navi Mumbai.

V. RESULTS & DATA ANALYSIS

Table 10(refer to the next page) shows the preference and duration of social media apps used by our samples. The mentioned apps are popular and frequently used in general. According to data, it can be seen out of 298 samples, WhatsApp shows 118 samples use it for 1-2 hours, 69 of them use it less than 1 hour, 68 samples use it for 3-4 hours, 34 samples use it for 5-6 hours and only 9 samples use it for more than 6 hours. Facebook shows 157 samples use it for less than 1 hour, 79 of them use it for 1-2 hours, 44 samples use it for 3-4 hours, 17 samples use it for 5-6 hours and only 1 sample use it for more than 6 hours.

YouTube shows 152 samples use it for less than 1 hour, 92 of them use it for 1-2 hours, 40 samples use it for 3-4 hours, 12 samples use it for 5-6 hours and only 2 samples use it for more than 6 hours. Instagram shows 172 samples use it for less than 1 hour, 75 of them use it for 1-2 hours, 33 samples use it for 3-4 hours, 15 samples use it for 5-6 hours and only 3 samples use it for more than 6 hours. Twitter shows 255 samples use it for less than 1 hour, 28 of them use it for 1-2 hours, 11 samples use it for 3-4 hours, 4 samples use it for 5-6 hours and no sample use it for more than 6 hours.

Snapchat shows 281 samples use it for less than 1 hour, 13 of them use it for 1-2 hours, 4 samples use it for 3-4 hours, no sample uses it for more than 5 hours. Pinterest

shows 266 samples use it for less than 1 hour, 23 of them use it for 1-2 hours, 6 samples use it for 3-4 hours, 2 samples use it for 5-6 hours and only 1 sample use it for more than 6 hours. Usage of others apps shows 261 samples use it for less than 1 hour, 28 of them use it for 1-2 hours, 7 samples use it for 3-4 hours, 1 samples use it for 5-6 hours and only 1 sample use it for more than 6 hours.

According to the amount of time spent on each social networking platform, the majority of the participants spent the most of their time on WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube and Instagram. While the least time was spent on Snapchat, Twitter, Pinterest and other apps.

Table 7 shows the duration of time spent on social media apps during weekdays and weekends. According to the data, it can be seen that on weekdays, 112 participants spend their time on social media apps for 1-2 hours, 79 of them spend for 3-4 hours, 77 of them spend for 1-2 hours, 24 of them spend for 5-6 hours and only 6 participants spend more than 6 hours. On the other hand, 101 participants spend their time on social media apps for 3-4 hours, 91 of them spend for 1-2 hours, 62 of them spend less than 1 hour, 32 of them spend for 5-6 hours and only 12 participants spend more than 6 hours. It can be seen that the majority of the samples spend 1-2 hours on weekdays and more than 3 hours on weekends.

Duration	Weekdays	Weekends
Less than 1 hour	77 (25.83 %)	62 (20.80 %)
1-2 hours	112 (37.58 %)	91 (30.53 %)
3-4 hours	79 (26.51 %)	101 (33.89 %)
5-6 hours	24 (8.05 %)	32 (10.73 %)
More than 6 hours	6 (2.01 %)	12 (4.20 %)

Table 7: Social Media usage on weekdays / weekends

Content Engagement	Number of women
Educational Purpose	97 (32.55 %)
Entertainment	233 (78.18 %)
Infotainment (Eg. GK)	50 (16.77 %)
Learning a new skill	147 (49.32 %)
News/ Latest updates	140 (46.97 %)
Politics	34 (11.40 %)
Religion	58 (19.46 %)
Work Purpose	68 (22.81 %)
Others	6 (2.01 %)

Table 8: Social Media content engagement

As shown in the above Table 8, according to the data collected, the majority of the samples use social media platforms for entertainment (78.18), learning a new skill (49.32), listening to news and latest updates (46.97) and for educational purposes (32.55).

Activity	Number of women
Due to boredom	54 (18.12 %)
Free time	196 (65.77 %)
Holidays	6 (2.01 %)
Traveling	20 (6.71 %)
While having meals	5 (1.67 %)
Social Situations	3 (1 %)
Others	14 (4.69 %)

Table 9: Access to social media

Duration	Whatsapp	Facebook	YouTube	Instagram	Twitter	Snapchat	Pinterest	Others
Less than 1 hr	69	157	152	172	255	281	266	261
1-2 hours	118	79	92	75	28	13	23	28
3-4 hours	68	44	40	33	11	4	6	7
5-6 hours	34	17	12	15	4	0	2	1
More than 6 hrs	9	1	2	3	0	0	1	1

Table 10: Social Media apps preferred

As shown in Table 9 below, according to the data collected, the majority of the samples access social media platforms during their free time (65.77), or due to boredom (18.12) or while traveling (6.71).

Table 11 shows data of the addiction level based on age. The range was categorized into 4 groups which were low (Below 84), moderate (85-100), high (101-121), and very high (122-147). According to data, the samples which belong to 40 years of age consist of 64 samples, out of which 47 showed low level, 14 showed moderate level, 3 showed high level and zero showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 41 years of age consist of 31 samples, 22 showed low level, 5 showed moderate, 3 showed high level and zero showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 42 years of age consist of 36 samples, 25 showed low level, 4 showed moderate, 6 showed high level and only 1 showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 43 years of age consist of 38 samples, 29 showed low level, 7 showed moderate, 2 showed high level and no sample showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 44 years of age consist of 41 samples, 31 showed low level, 8 showed moderate, 2 showed high level and no sample showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 45 years of age consist of 88 samples, 72 showed low level, 12 showed moderate, 3 showed high level and only 1 showed a very high level of addiction.

and only 1 showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 42 years of age consist of 36 samples, 25 showed low level, 4 showed moderate, 6 showed high level and only 1 showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 43 years of age consist of 38 samples, 29 showed low level, 7 showed moderate, 2 showed high level and no sample showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 44 years of age consist of 41 samples, 31 showed low level, 8 showed moderate, 2 showed high level and no sample showed a very high level of addiction. Samples belonging to 45 years of age consist of 88 samples, 72 showed low level, 12 showed moderate, 3 showed high level and only 1 showed a very high level of addiction.

Age	Number (of women)	Below 84 - Low	85-100 - Moderate	101-121 - High	122-147 Very High
40	64	47 (73.43 %)	14 (21.87 %)	3 (4.68 %)	0
41	31	22 (70.96 %)	5 (16.12 %)	3 (9.67 %)	1 (3.22 %)
42	36	25 (69.44 %)	4 (11.11 %)	6 (16.66 %)	1 (2.77 %)
43	38	29 (76.31 %)	7 (18.42 %)	2 (5.26 %)	0
44	41	31 (75.60 %)	8 (19.51 %)	2 (4.87 %)	0
45	88	72 (81.81 %)	12 (13.63 %)	3 (3.40 %)	1 (1.13 %)

Table 11: Addiction level (age-wise) in total

Employment Status	Number	Low – below 84	Moderate 85-100	High 101-121	Very High 122-147
Employed	173	136 (78.61 %)	24 (13.87 %)	11 (6.35 %)	2 (1.15 %)
Unemployed	125	92 (73.6 %)	23 (18.4 %)	9 (7.2%)	1 (0.8 %)

Table 12: Addiction level (Employment Status) in total

Table 12 shows data of the addiction level based on employment (working and non-working women). The range was categorized into 4 groups which were low (Below 84), moderate (85-100), high (101-121), and very high (122-147). According to data, out of our total 298 samples, 173 were working women and 125 were non-working women. Samples belonging to 173 working women, 136 showed low level, 24 showed moderate level, 11 showed high level and 2 of them showed very high level. Samples belonging to 125 non-working women, 92 showed low level, 23 showed moderate level, 9 showed high level and only 1 showed very high level.

VI. DISSCUSSION

In my study, social media addiction level overall, was low among women belonging to the age group of 40-45 years. It showed that 57.14 percent of working women had shown low levels of social media addiction while 28.5 percent and 14.15 percent showed moderate and high levels of social media addiction respectively. Also in the non-working women category, I was able to find out that 57.89 percent of these women were having low levels of social media addiction while 42.1 percent and 0 percent showed moderate and high levels of social media addiction respectively.

The current study agrees with a few other studies that show that there was no significant difference between men and women in terms of mobile phone addiction, communication disturbance, sadness, and loneliness. Women were shown to be more obsessed with their phones than men which were conducted by Ivanova et al, 2020. The brief assessments during the COVID-19 outbreak also revealed that more than 80% of respondents said they were frequently exposed to social media stated by David & Warriar (2021).

According to research by Aydin et al. (2021), 99.5% of the participants were using the internet on a regular basis, with nearly half using it for 1-3 hours, 20.5 % doing so for 4 to 6 hours, 19.3 % doing so for just under an hour, and 8.1 % doing so for more than 7 hours. Social media experience among participants was found to be 8 years on average. However, a few points closely resemble my research. The survey done by Aydin et al (2021) indicates that 50.4 % preferred Instagram while 23.9 % preferred Facebook, yet certain results are quite similar to my research. The age group with the greatest degree of internet addiction, according to mean scores, is determined to be 18 to 25 years old. Rather, the participants who were employed were found to have the lowest score for depression.

Aydin et al.'s study (2021) also indicated that both the SMAS (Social media Addiction Scaled) overall score, as well as the Busyness sub-scale, were significantly influenced by the marriage status of the participants. It may be claimed that because of their increased family responsibilities, married individuals have much less leisure time to spend on social networking sites than singles in this regard. The amount of hours invested in social media varies by occupation and is less for working persons than for students or job hunters.

As the study showed some symptoms like letting social media control their mood and how it is difficult to cut off their screen time, I came across a study by Hou et al (2019) which corresponds with my research. People struggling with poor psychological health and emotional well-being, commonly use social networking sites to elevate their spirits, as per this study. Therefore, it is plausible that there is a symbiotic connection between dependency on the internet and poor psychological health (Hou et al, 2019).

Facebook was among the most popular social networking applications, according to my research. Similar to the last example, self-esteem only marginally predicted Facebook addiction. In accordance with the research conducted by David & Warriar (2021), the frequency of addiction to Facebook was 39.7%. They said that women use cell phones more frequently than men do. The research's findings showed how earnest male students' performances were. In contrast to males who disregarded their studies, experienced anxiety, and lost grip over themselves, female students, when developmental changes and views were excluded, were rarely impacted by the impacts of mobile phone addiction. Additionally, it was shown that contrary to my study, more than 80% of the participants also self-reported regularly using digital platforms.

The recent study also demonstrates the tendency for people to use social media more when they're free or bored than when they're in social settings. As per my analysis of the research, approximately 72.34 percent of women engage in social media usage in their free time. Whereas, approximately 8.5 percent of women engage in it out of boredom. These findings also correlate to the results of the study conducted by David & Warriar (2021). The 203 young individuals (aged 18 to 30) who participated in the study—some of whom were single, wedded, or engaged—were surveyed online via the Google questionnaire to gather the data. A sample of the t-test was used to compute the inter-item validity, reliability, and consistency coefficient (Davids, S., 2021). The majority of respondents were found to be keen to utilize social media and explore online platforms in order to stay updated on the material posted by their respective groups on social media, according to the study's findings. Additionally, individuals frequently spend more time online, particularly on social networking sites, while they are alone as opposed to whenever they are among other people.

VII. CONCLUSION

This research confirms that the level of social media addiction was respectively low in working and non-working women of age group 40-45 years. The results of this study were obtained based on the employment status and age of these women. It states that 78.61 percent of working women had shown low levels of social media addiction while 6.35 percent and only 1.15 percent showed high and very high levels of social media addiction respectively. Also in the non-working women category, I was able to find out that 73.6 percent of these women were having low levels of social media addiction while 7.2 percent and only 0.8 percent showed high and very high levels of social media addiction. The data also inferred that the lowest level addiction was found in the age of 45 years old women and highest was found in 42 years old women, respectively. In addition to that, the majority of the samples access social media platforms during their free time, due to boredom and while traveling. It was also observed that WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook and YouTube were mostly used and they spend time on these social networking apps more during weekends than on weekdays. Entertainment, learning new skills and latest news and updates were the content usually preferred by this age group of women. Based on the information gathered, it was also found that there were 7.71 percent of women who were addicted to social media and showed a high level of addiction. They showed some symptoms like letting social media control their mood and how it is difficult to cut off their screen time.

Social media had emerged to be one of the most crucial means of disseminating information during the outbreak, with unmatched supremacy in terms of speed, scope, and impact (Merchant & Lurie, 2020). Adults had become more likely to utilize internet sources than they were to use traditional media to follow disaster-related news (Jones, Garfin, Holman, & Silver, 2016). In this sense, it was rather interesting to observe that even with the uncertainty of the COVID-19 pandemic being in play, the working and non-

working women of the age group 40-45 years were mainly unaffected by the high level of social media usage in their daily lives.

[11.] Merchant, R.M. , & Lurie, N. (2020). Social media and emergency preparedness in response to novel coronavirus. *JAMA*, 323(20), 2011–2012.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Al-Samarraie, H., Bello, K.-A., Alzahrani, A. I., Smith, A. P., & Emele, C. (2021). Young users' social media addiction: causes, consequences and preventions. *Information Technology & People, ahead-of-print* (ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/itp-11-2020-0753>
- [2.] Ayeni, P.T., (2019). *Social Media Addiction: Symptoms and Way Forward*. Vol 1, issue (1). 19 - 42. ISSN (e): 2642-7478
- [3.] Aydin, S.; Koçak, O.; Shaw, T.A.; Buber, B.; Akpınar, E.Z.; Younis, M.Z., (2019). *Investigation of the Effect of Social Media Addiction on Adults with Depression*. *Healthcare* 2021, 9, 450. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9040450>
- [4.] David, S., & Warriar, U. (2021). Social media addiction among Indian young adults during COVID-19. *Parikalpana: KIIT Journal of Management*, 17(1), <https://doi.org/10.23862/kiit-parikalpana/2021/v17/i1/209027>
- [5.] Dhingra, Manish and Mudgal, Rakesh K., (2019). Historical Evolution of Social Media: An Overview. International Conference on Advances in Engineering Science Management & Technology (ICAESMT) - 2019, Uttarakhand University, Dehradun, India, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3395665> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3395665>
- [6.] Fullerton, N., (2021). *Instagram vs. Reality: The Pandemic's Impact on social media and Mental Health*. *Penn Medicine News*. <https://www.pennmedicine.org/news/news-blog/2021/april/instagram-vs-reality-the-pandemics-impact-on-social-media-and-mental-health>
- [7.] Hou, Y., Xiong, D., Jiang, T., Song, L., & Wang, Q. (2019). Social media addiction: Its impact, mediation, and intervention. *Cyberpsychology*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.5817/cp2019-1-4>
- [8.] Shahnaz, I., & Karim, A. K. M. R. (2014). The impact of internet addiction on life satisfaction and life engagement in young adults. *Universal Journal of Psychology*, 2(9), 273–284. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujp.2014.020902>
- [9.] Zhao, L. (2021). The impact of social media use types and social media addiction on subjective well-being of college students: A comparative analysis of addicted and non-addicted students. *Computers in Human Behavior Reports*, 4(100122), 100122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbr.2021.100122>
- [10.] Zhao, N., & Zhou, G. (2020). Social Media Use and Mental Health during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Moderator Role of Disaster Stressor and Mediator Role of Negative Affect. In *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being* (Vol. 12, Issue 4, pp. 1019–1038). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aphw.12226>